

Raport statystyczny

Comparison of LGN Measurements Performed by Four Independent Technicians

```
dane$lgn_rh_2[dane$lgn_rh_2 %in% c("brak", "n/d", "", "NA")] <- NA
dane$lgn_rh_2 <- as.numeric(dane$lgn_rh_2)

dane <- dane %>%
  mutate(across(c(lgn_rh_1, lgn_rh_2, lgn_rh_3, lgn_rh_4), ~ as.numeric(.)))
```

Statistics

Zmienna	Średnia	SD	Mediana	Min	Max	Ilość
lgn_lh_1	100.17105	16.97829	100.250	63.5	131.0	38
lgn_lh_2	100.78211	16.57617	96.635	68.6	137.0	38
lgn_lh_3	94.50263	14.11982	92.150	63.5	126.3	38
lgn_lh_4	94.91579	12.55897	90.900	76.4	124.8	38
lgn_rh_1	109.29737	14.83004	108.050	69.5	135.4	38
lgn_rh_2	109.55270	16.26565	109.700	76.7	137.0	37
lgn_rh_3	106.47368	14.71472	107.600	73.7	130.1	38
lgn_rh_4	105.47105	11.59825	103.400	82.4	128.6	38

Normality test

A Shapiro–Wilk normality test was performed for each operator independently, stratified by LGN left and LGN right measurements.

Zmienna	Wartość_W	p_wartość
lgn_lh_1	0.981	0.76242
lgn_lh_2	0.944	0.05617
lgn_lh_3	0.968	0.33845
lgn_lh_4	0.935	0.02987
lgn_rh_1	0.966	0.29946
lgn_rh_2	0.967	0.32884

Zmienna	Wartość	p_wartość
lgn_rh_3	0.964	0.25294
lgn_rh_4	0.977	0.59545

ANOVA LGN left

Levene'a

```
dane_filtr <- dane %>%
  filter(group %in% c("NTG", "HTG", "K")) %>%
  select(group, lgn_lh_1, lgn_lh_2, lgn_lh_3, lgn_lh_4) %>%
  mutate(across(starts_with("lgn_lh"), as.numeric))

dane_long <- dane_filtr %>%
  pivot_longer(
    cols = starts_with("lgn_lh"),
    names_to = "Pomiar",
    values_to = "Wartosc"
  )

leveneTest(Wartosc ~ group, data = dane_long)

Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)
  Df F value Pr(>F)
group 2  5.1603 0.00681 **
    149
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

dane_long <- dane %>%
  pivot_longer(
    cols = c("lgn_lh_1", "lgn_lh_2", "lgn_lh_3", "lgn_lh_4"),
    names_to = "Grupa",
    values_to = "Wartosc"
  )

wynik_kw <- kruskal.test(Wartosc ~ Grupa, data = dane_long)

chi2_stat <- round(unnamed(wynik_kw$statistic), 3)
df_kw      <- wynik_kw$parameter
p_wart    <- signif(wynik_kw$p.value, 5)

glue("
### Kruskal-Wallis test for LGN_lh (Grupa: lgn_lh_1 - lgn_lh_4)
- Chi² = {chi2_stat}
- df = {df_kw}
- p-value = {p_wart}
")
```

```
### Kruskal-Wallis test for LGN_lh (Grupa: lgn_lh_1 - lgn_lh_4)
- Chi2 = 4.744
- df = 3
- p-value = 0.19153
```

ANOVA LGN right

Levene's test

```
dane_filtr <- dane %>%
  filter(group %in% c("NTG", "HTG", "K")) %>%
  select(group, lgn_rh_1, lgn_rh_2, lgn_rh_3, lgn_rh_4) %>%
  mutate(across(starts_with("lgn_rh"), as.numeric))
```

```
dane_long <- dane_filtr %>%
  pivot_longer(
    cols = starts_with("lgn_rh"),
    names_to = "Pomiar",
    values_to = "Wartosc"
  )
```

```
leveneTest(Wartosc ~ group, data = dane_long)
```

Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance (center = median)

group	Df	F value	Pr(>F)
2	0.3702	0.6912	
148			

```
dane <- dane %>%
  mutate(across(c(lgn_rh_1, lgn_rh_2, lgn_rh_3, lgn_rh_4), ~ as.numeric(.)))
```

Test ANOVA dla LGN_rh (Grupa: lgn_rh_1 - lgn_rh_4)

- Statystyka F = 0.751
- Stopnie swobody: grupa = 3, reszta = 147
- p-value = 0.52334

LGN LEFT

group	Średnia	SD	Mediana	Min	Max
HTG	93.11	8.96	94.43	76.26	107.28
K	105.99	13.26	103.70	84.62	126.03
NTG	91.36	12.15	90.85	68.55	118.83

Shapiro-Wilk test for LGN_lh (grupa 'NTG')

- Statystyka W = 0.945
- p-value = 0.5296

Shapiro-Wilk test for LGN_lh (grupa 'HTG')

- Statystyka W = 0.952
- p-value = 0.6907

Shapiro-Wilk test for LGN_lh (grupa 'K')

- Statystyka W = 0.949
- p-value = 0.5041

Levene's test

Test Levene'a dla LGN_lh

- Statystyka F = 1.331
- p-value = 0.2773

OK

ANOVA for LGN_lh ~ group (tylko NTG, HTG, K)

- Statystyka F = 6.228
- Stopnie swobody: grupa = 2, reszta = 35
- p-value = 0.00485347249486256

Test ANOVA dla LGN_lh ~ group (tylko NTG, HTG, K)

- Statystyka F = 6.228
- Stopnie swobody: grupa = 2, reszta = 35
- p-value = 0.00485347249486256 Comparision p_value NTG-K NTG-K 0.00713 K-HTG K-HTG 0.03127 NTG-HTG NTG-HTG 0.93530

LGN RIGHT

group	Średnia	SD	Mediana	Min	Max
HTG	108.62	11.69	112.28	89.50	127.00
K	110.96	10.68	110.00	96.70	125.38
NTG	103.25	13.85	103.68	78.67	125.62

Test Shapiro-Wilka dla LGN_rh (grupa 'NTG')

- Statystyka W = 0.972
- p-value = 0.9127

Test Shapiro-Wilka dla LGN_rh (grupa 'HTG')

- Statystyka W = 0.929

- p-value = 0.4376

Shapiro-Wilk test for LGN_rh (grupa 'K')

- Statystyka W = 0.89
- p-value = 0.06768

Levene's test LGN right

Test Levene'a dla LGN_rh

- Statystyka F = 0.262
- p-value = 0.7713

ANOVA LGN right

Test ANOVA dla LGN_rh ~ group (tylko NTG, HTG, K)

- Statystyka F = 1.451
- Stopnie swobody: grupa = 2, reszta = 35
- p-value = 0.248090201775825

Appendix - ANOVA + Cohen's etc

LEFT LGN

```
suppressPackageStartupMessages({
  library(dplyr); library(tidyr); library(glue); library(broom)
  library(emmeans); library(effectsize); library(rstatix)
  library(sandwich); library(lmtest); library(purrr); library(gt)
})

dane_filtr <- dane %>%
  filter(group %in% c("NTG", "HTG", "K")) %>%
  mutate(group = factor(group, levels = c("NTG", "HTG", "K"))) %>%
  select(group, LGN_lh) %>%
  tidyr::drop_na(LGN_lh)

# ===== ANOVA =====
fit <- aov(LGN_lh ~ group, data = dane_filtr)
sum_aov <- summary(fit)
F_stat <- unname(sum_aov[[1]]$`F value`[1])
p_val <- unname(sum_aov[[1]]$`Pr(>F)`[1])
df1 <- sum_aov[[1]]$Df[1]
df2 <- sum_aov[[1]]$Df[2]

eta2_df <- suppressMessages(effectsize::eta_squared(fit, partial = TRUE, ci =
0.95))
eta_col <- if ("Eta2_partial" %in% names(eta2_df)) "Eta2_partial" else "Eta2"
```

```

omni_tbl <- tibble::tibble(
  Outcome = "LGN_lh",
  Test = "ANOVA (one-way)",
  Statistic = sprintf("F(%d, %d) = %.2f", df1, df2, F_stat),
  `p-value` = ifelse(p_val < 0.001, "<0.001", sprintf("%.3f", p_val)),
  `η² (95% CI)` = sprintf("%.3f [%%.3f, %%.3f]",
                          eta2_df[[eta_col]][1], eta2_df$CI_low[1],
eta2_df$CI_high[1])
)

emm <- emmeans::emmeans(fit, ~ group)
tukey_ci <- summary(pairs(emm, adjust = "tukey"), infer = c(TRUE, TRUE)) %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  transmute(
    Comparison = gsub(" ", "", contrast), # "NTG-HTG" itd.
    `Δ_mean [95% CI]` = sprintf("%.2f [% .2f, % .2f]", estimate, lower.CL,
upper.CL),
    `p (Tukey)` = ifelse(p.value < 0.001, "<0.001", sprintf("%.3f",
p.value)),
    p_num = p.value
  )

pair_key <- function(a,b) paste(sort(c(a,b)), collapse = "__")
pairs_list <- combn(levels(dane_filtr$group), 2, simplify = FALSE)

d_pairs <- map_dfr(pairs_list, function(p) {
  sub <- filter(dane_filtr, group %in% p) %>% droplevels()
  res <- effectsize::cohens_d(LGN_lh ~ group, data = sub,
                             pooled_sd = TRUE, hedges.correction = FALSE, ci
= 0.95)
  tibble::tibble(
    key = pair_key(p[1], p[2]),
    `Cohen's d [95% CI]` = sprintf("%.2f [%%.2f, %%.2f]", res$Cohens_d[1],
res$CI_low[1], res$CI_high[1])
  ) %>% mutate(Comparison = paste(p[1], p[2], sep = "-"))
})

g_pairs <- map_dfr(pairs_list, function(p) {
  sub <- filter(dane_filtr, group %in% p) %>% droplevels()
  res <- effectsize::hedges_g(LGN_lh ~ group, data = sub, ci = 0.95)
  tibble::tibble(
    key = pair_key(p[1], p[2]),
    `Hedges' g [95% CI]` = sprintf("%.2f [%%.2f, %%.2f]", res$Hedges_g[1],
res$CI_low[1], res$CI_high[1])
  ) %>% mutate(Comparison = paste(p[1], p[2], sep = "-"))
})

tukey_keyed <- tukey_ci %>%
  mutate(key = vapply(strsplit(Comparison, "-"), function(x) pair_key(x[1],

```

```

x[2]), "")

posthoc_tbl <- tukey_keyed %>%
  left_join(d_pairs %>% select(key, `Cohen's d [95% CI]`), by = "key") %>%
  left_join(g_pairs %>% select(key, `Hedges' g [95% CI]`), by = "key") %>%
  select(Comparison, `Δ_mean [95% CI]`, `p (Tukey)`, `Cohen's d [95% CI]`,
`Hedges' g [95% CI]`, p_num) %>%
  arrange(p_num) %>%
  select(-p_num)

gt_omni <- omni_tbl %>%
  gt() %>%
  tab_header(
    title = md("***LGN<sub>left</sub> ~ group: omnibus test**")
  ) %>%
  cols_align(everything(), align = "center") %>%
  tab_style(
    style = list(cell_text(weight = "bold")),
    locations = cells_body(columns = vars(`p-value`), rows =
as.numeric(gsub("<", "", `p-value`) < 0.05 | `p-value` == "<0.001")
  )

gt_posthoc <- posthoc_tbl %>%
  gt() %>%
  tab_header(
    title = md("***LGN<sub>left</sub> ~ group: Tukey post hoc & effect
sizes**")
  ) %>%
  cols_label(
    Comparison = "Comparison",
    `Δ_mean [95% CI]` = html("&Delta; mean [95% CI]"),
    `p (Tukey)` = "p (Tukey)",
    `Cohen's d [95% CI]` = "Cohen's d [95% CI]",
    `Hedges' g [95% CI]` = "Hedges' g [95% CI]"
  ) %>%
  fmt_markdown(columns = everything()) %>%
  cols_align(everything(), align = "center") %>%
  tab_style(
    style = list(cell_text(weight = "bold")),
    locations = cells_body(columns = vars(`p (Tukey)`),
rows = as.numeric(gsub("<", "", `p (Tukey)`) < 0.05
| `p (Tukey)` == "<0.001")
  )

gt_omni

```

Table 1: LGNleft ~ group: omnibus test

Outcome	Test	Statistic	p-value	η^2 (95% CI)
LGN_lh	ANOVA (one-way)	F(2, 35) = 6.23	0.005	0.262 [0.060, 1.000]

```
gt_posthoc
```

Table 2: LGNleft ~ group: Tukey post hoc & effect sizes

Comparison	Δ mean [95% CI]	p (Tukey)	Cohen's d [95% CI]	Hedges' g [95% CI]
NTG-K	-14.63 [-25.66, -3.59]	0.007	-1.15 [-1.94, -0.33]	-1.11 [-1.89, -0.32]
HTG-K	-12.88 [-24.77, -0.99]	0.031	-1.09 [-1.94, -0.22]	-1.06 [-1.88, -0.22]
NTG-HTG	-1.74 [-13.99, 10.50]	0.935	-0.16 [-0.98, 0.67]	-0.15 [-0.95, 0.64]

```
suppressPackageStartupMessages({
  library(dplyr); library(tidyr); library(glue); library(broom)
  library(emmeans); library(effectsize); library(gt)
})

get_col <- function(df, candidates) {
  x <- intersect(candidates, names(df))
  if (length(x)) x[1] else NA_character_
}

dane_filtr_rh <- dane %>%
  filter(group %in% c("NTG", "HTG", "K")) %>%
  mutate(group = factor(group, levels = c("NTG", "HTG", "K"))) %>%
  select(group, LGN_rh) %>%
  tidyr::drop_na(LGN_rh)

# ===== ANOVA =====
fit_rh <- aov(LGN_rh ~ group, data = dane_filtr_rh)
sum_aov_rh <- summary(fit_rh)
F_stat <- unname(sum_aov_rh[[1]]$`F value`[1])
p_val <- unname(sum_aov_rh[[1]]$`Pr(>F)`[1])
df1 <- sum_aov_rh[[1]]$Df[1]
df2 <- sum_aov_rh[[1]]$Df[2]

eta2_df_rh <- suppressMessages(effectsize::eta_squared(fit_rh, partial =
TRUE, ci = 0.95))
eta_col <- if ("Eta2_partial" %in% names(eta2_df_rh)) "Eta2_partial" else
"Eta2"

omni_tbl_rh <- tibble::tibble(
  Outcome = "LGN_rh",
  Test = "ANOVA (one-way)",
  Statistic = sprintf("F(%d, %d) = %.2f", df1, df2, F_stat),
  p = ifelse(p_val < 0.001, "<0.001", sprintf("%.3f", p_val)),
  p_num = p_val, # do stylowania
  `η²_95CI` = sprintf("%.3f [%.3f, %.3f]",
```

```

      eta2_df_rh[[eta_col]][1], eta2_df_rh$CI_low[1],
eta2_df_rh$CI_high[1])
)

gt_omni_rh <- omni_tbl_rh %>%
  select(Outcome, Test, Statistic, p, `η²_95CI`) %>%
  gt() %>%
  tab_header(
    title = md("**LGN<sub>right</sub> ~ group: omnibus test**")
  ) %>%
  cols_label(
    Outcome = "Outcome",
    Test = "Test",
    Statistic = "Statistic",
    p = "p",
    `η²_95CI` = html("&eta;<sup>2</sup> [95% CI]")
  ) %>%
  cols_align(everything(), align = "center")

emm_rh <- emmeans::emmeans(fit_rh, ~ group)
tukey_rh <- summary(pairs(emm_rh, adjust = "tukey"), infer = c(TRUE, TRUE))
%>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  transmute(
    Comparison = gsub(" ", "", contrast), # "NTG-HTG" itd.
    Delta_CI = sprintf("%.2f [% .2f, % .2f]", estimate, lower.CL,
upper.CL),
    p_Tukey = ifelse(p.value < 0.001, "<0.001", sprintf("%.3f", p.value)),
    p_num = p.value
  )

pair_key <- function(a, b) paste(sort(c(a,b)), collapse="__")
pairs_list <- combn(levels(dane_filtr_rh$group), 2, simplify = FALSE)

d_pairs_rh <- purrr::map_dfr(pairs_list, function(p) {
  sub <- dplyr::filter(dane_filtr_rh, group %in% p) %>% droplevels()
  res <- effectsize::cohens_d(LGN_rh ~ group, data = sub,
    pooled_sd = TRUE, hedges.correction = FALSE, ci
= 0.95)
  d_col <- get_col(res, c("Cohens_d", "Cohen_s_d", "d"))
  tibble::tibble(
    key = pair_key(p[1], p[2]),
    d_CI = sprintf("%.2f [% .2f, % .2f]",
      as.numeric(res[[d_col]][1]),
      as.numeric(res$CI_low[1]),
      as.numeric(res$CI_high[1]))
  ) %>% mutate(Comparison = paste(p[1], p[2], sep = "-"))
})

```

```

g_pairs_rh <- purrr::map_dfr(pairs_list, function(p) {
  sub <- dplyr::filter(dane_filtr_rh, group %in% p) %>% droplevels()
  res <- effectsize::hedges_g(LGN_rh ~ group, data = sub, ci = 0.95)
  g_col <- get_col(res, c("Hedges_g", "g"))
  tibble::tibble(
    key      = pair_key(p[1], p[2]),
    g_CI     = sprintf("%.2f [%.2f, %.2f]",
                      as.numeric(res[[g_col]][1]),
                      as.numeric(res$CI_low[1]),
                      as.numeric(res$CI_high[1]))
  ) %>% mutate(Comparison = paste(p[1], p[2], sep = "-"))
})

tukey_keyed_rh <- tukey_rh %>%
  mutate(key = vapply(strsplit(Comparison, "-"), function(x) pair_key(x[1],
x[2]), ""))

posthoc_tbl_rh <- tukey_keyed_rh %>%
  left_join(d_pairs_rh %>% select(key, d_CI), by = "key") %>%
  left_join(g_pairs_rh %>% select(key, g_CI), by = "key") %>%
  select(Comparison, Delta_CI, p_Tukey, d_CI, g_CI, p_num) %>%
  arrange(p_num) %>%
  select(-p_num)

gt_posthoc_rh <- posthoc_tbl_rh %>%
  gt() %>%
  tab_header(
    title = md("***LGN<sub>right</sub> ~ group: Tukey post hoc & effect
sizes**")
  ) %>%
  cols_label(
    Comparison = "Comparison",
    Delta_CI   = html("&Delta; mean [95% CI]"),
    p_Tukey    = "p (Tukey)",
    d_CI       = "Cohen's d [95% CI]",
    g_CI       = "Hedges' g [95% CI]"
  ) %>%
  cols_align(everything(), align = "center")

gt_omni_rh

```

Table 3: LGN_{right} ~ group: omnibus test

Outcome	Test	Statistic	p	η^2 [95% CI]
LGN_rh	ANOVA (one-way)	F(2, 35) = 1.45	0.248	0.077 [0.000, 1.000]

```
gt_posthoc_rh
```

Table 4: LGNright ~ group: Tukey post hoc & effect sizes

Comparison	Δ mean [95% CI]	p (Tukey)	Cohen's d [95% CI]	Hedges' g [95% CI]
NTG-K	-7.71 [-18.93, 3.52]	0.227	-0.63 [-1.39, 0.14]	-0.61 [-1.35, 0.13]
NTG-HTG	-5.37 [-17.83, 7.09]	0.548	-0.41 [-1.24, 0.42]	-0.40 [-1.20, 0.41]
HTG-K	-2.34 [-14.43, 9.75]	0.884	-0.21 [-1.01, 0.59]	-0.20 [-0.98, 0.57]

```
suppressPackageStartupMessages({
  library(dplyr); library(tidyr); library(glue); library(broom)
  library(emmeans); library(effectsize); library(gt); library(purrr);
  library(rstatix)
})

pair_key <- function(a, b) paste(sort(c(a,b)), collapse="__")
get_col <- function(df, candidates) { x <- intersect(candidates,
names(df)); if (length(x)) x[1] else NA_character_ }

make_tables <- function(dat, value_col, group_col = "group",
  levels = c("NTG", "HTG", "K"),
  outcome_label = NULL) {

  dat1 <- dat %>%
    filter(.data[[group_col]] %in% levels) %>%
    mutate(!group_col := factor(.data[[group_col]], levels = levels)) %>%
    select(all_of(c(group_col, value_col))) %>%
    tidyr::drop_na()

  desc <- dat1 %>%
    group_by(.data[[group_col]]) %>%
    summarise(n = dplyr::n(),
      m = mean(.data[[value_col]]),
      sd = sd(.data[[value_col]]),
      .groups = "drop") %>%
    mutate(msd = sprintf("%.1f \u00B1 %.1f", m, sd)) %>%
    select(group = !group_col, n, msd)

  form <- stats::as.formula(paste(value_col, "~", group_col))
  fit <- aov(form, data = dat1)
  sumA <- summary(fit)
  Fv <- unname(sumA[[1]]$`F value`[1])
  pv <- unname(sumA[[1]]$`Pr(>F)`[1])
  df1 <- sumA[[1]]$Df[1]; df2 <- sumA[[1]]$Df[2]

  eta2_df <- suppressMessages(effectsize::eta_squared(fit, partial = TRUE, ci
= 0.95))
  eta_col <- if ("Eta2_partial" %in% names(eta2_df)) "Eta2_partial" else
```

```

"Eta2"
  eta_txt <- sprintf("%.3f [%.3f, %.3f]", eta2_df[[eta_col]][1],
eta2_df$CI_low[1], eta2_df$CI_high[1])

wide_desc <- tidyr::pivot_wider(
  desc,
  names_from = group, values_from = c(n, msd),
  names_glue = "{group}_{.value}"
)

outcome <- if (is.null(outcome_label)) value_col else outcome_label

omni_tbl <- wide_desc %>%
  mutate(Outcome = outcome,
    Statistic = sprintf("F(%d, %d) = %.2f", df1, df2, Fv),
    p = ifelse(pv < 0.001, "<0.001", sprintf("%.3f", pv)),
    p_num = pv,
    eta2 = eta_txt) %>%
  select(
    Outcome,
    paste0(levels[1], "_n"), paste0(levels[1], "_msd"),
    paste0(levels[2], "_n"), paste0(levels[2], "_msd"),
    paste0(levels[3], "_n"), paste0(levels[3], "_msd"),
    Statistic, p, eta2, p_num
  )

omni_cols <- setdiff(colnames(omni_tbl), "p_num")

gt_omni <- omni_tbl %>%
  select(all_of(omni_cols)) %>%
  gt() %>%
  tab_header(title = md("**Descriptives & omnibus (ANOVA) with  $\eta^2$  [95%
CI]**")) %>%
  cols_label(
    Outcome = "Outcome",
    !!paste0(levels[1], "_n") := paste0(levels[1], " n"),
    !!paste0(levels[1], "_msd") := paste0(levels[1], " Mean\u00B11SD"),
    !!paste0(levels[2], "_n") := paste0(levels[2], " n"),
    !!paste0(levels[2], "_msd") := paste0(levels[2], " Mean\u00B11SD"),
    !!paste0(levels[3], "_n") := paste0(levels[3], " n"),
    !!paste0(levels[3], "_msd") := paste0(levels[3], " Mean\u00B11SD"),
    Statistic = "ANOVA",
    p = "p",
    eta2 = html("&eta;<sup>2</sup> [95% CI]")
  ) %>%
  cols_align(align = "center", columns = everything())

```

```

emm <- emmeans::emmeans(fit, as.formula(paste0("~ ", group_col)))
tukey <- summary(pairs(emm, adjust = "tukey"), infer = c(TRUE, TRUE)) %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  transmute(
    Comparison = gsub(" ", "", contrast), # "NTG-HTG"
    `Δmean [95% CI]` = sprintf("%.2f [% .2f, % .2f]", estimate, lower.CL,
upper.CL),
    `p (Tukey)` = ifelse(p.value < 0.001, "<0.001", sprintf("%.3f",
p.value)),
    p_num = p.value
  )

gr_lev <- levels(dat1[[group_col]])
pairs_list <- combn(gr_lev, 2, simplify = FALSE)

d_pairs <- purrr::map_dfr(pairs_list, function(p) {
  sub <- dplyr::filter(dat1, .data[[group_col]] %in% p) %>% droplevels()
  res <- effectsize::cohens_d(form, data = sub,
                             pooled_sd = TRUE, hedges.correction = FALSE,
ci = 0.95)
  res_df <- as.data.frame(res)
  d_col <- get_col(res_df, c("Cohens_d", "Cohen_s_d", "d"))
  tibble::tibble(
    key = pair_key(p[1], p[2]),
    d_CI = sprintf("%.2f [% .2f, % .2f]",
                  as.numeric(res_df[[d_col]][1]),
                  as.numeric(res_df$CI_low[1]),
                  as.numeric(res_df$CI_high[1])
    ),
    Comparison = paste(p[1], p[2], sep = "-")
  )
})

g_pairs <- purrr::map_dfr(pairs_list, function(p) {
  sub <- dplyr::filter(dat1, .data[[group_col]] %in% p) %>% droplevels()
  res <- effectsize::hedges_g(form, data = sub, ci = 0.95)
  res_df <- as.data.frame(res)
  g_col <- get_col(res_df, c("Hedges_g", "g"))
  tibble::tibble(
    key = pair_key(p[1], p[2]),
    g_CI = sprintf("%.2f [% .2f, % .2f]",
                  as.numeric(res_df[[g_col]][1]),
                  as.numeric(res_df$CI_low[1]),
                  as.numeric(res_df$CI_high[1])
    ),
    Comparison = paste(p[1], p[2], sep = "-")
  )
})

```

```

})

tukey_keyed <- tukey %>%
  mutate(key = vapply(strsplit(Comparison, "-"),
                      function(x) pair_key(x[1], x[2]), ""))

posthoc <- tukey_keyed %>%
  left_join(d_pairs %>% select(key, `Cohen's d [95% CI]` = d_CI), by =
"key") %>%
  left_join(g_pairs %>% select(key, `Hedges' g [95% CI]` = g_CI), by =
"key") %>%
  select(Comparison, `Δmean [95% CI]`, `p (Tukey)`,
        `Cohen's d [95% CI]`, `Hedges' g [95% CI]`, p_num) %>%
  arrange(p_num) %>%
  select(-p_num)

gt_post <- posthoc %>%
  gt() %>%
  tab_header(title = md("***Pairwise comparisons (Tukey) & effect sizes**"))
%>%
  cols_align(align = "center", columns = everything()) %>%
  cols_label(
    Comparison = "Comparison",
    `Δmean [95% CI]` = html("&Delta; mean [95% CI]"),
    `p (Tukey)` = "p (Tukey)",
    `Cohen's d [95% CI]` = "Cohen's d [95% CI]",
    `Hedges' g [95% CI]` = "Hedges' g [95% CI]"
  )

list(omnibus = gt_omni, posthoc = gt_post)
}

dane <- dane %>%
  mutate(
    LGN_avg = ifelse(is.na(LGN_lh) & is.na(LGN_rh),
                    NA_real_,
                    rowMeans(cbind(LGN_lh, LGN_rh), na.rm = TRUE))
  )

tab_avg <- make_tables(dane, value_col = "LGN_avg", outcome_label = "LGN_avg
(mean of L & R)")

tab_avg$omnibus # Tabela A: n, Mean±SD + ANOVA + η² [95% CI]

```

Table 5: Descriptives & omnibus (ANOVA) with η^2 [95% CI]

Outcome	NTG n	NTG Mean±SD	HTG n	HTG Mean±SD	K n	K Mean±SD	ANOVA	p	η^2 [95% CI]
LGN_avg (mean of L & R)	13	97.3 ± 12.2	10	100.9 ± 8.5	15	108.5 ± 11.6	F(2, 35) = 3.69	0.035	0.174 [0.007, 1.000]

tab_avg\$posthoc # Tabela B: Tukey Δ mean [95% CI] + Cohen's d / Hedges' g

Table 6: Pairwise comparisons (Tukey) & effect sizes

Comparison	Δ mean [95% CI]	p (Tukey)	Cohen's d [95% CI]	Hedges' g [95% CI]
NTG-K	-11.17 [-21.48, -0.85]	0.031	-0.94 [-1.72, -0.15]	-0.91 [-1.67, -0.14]
HTG-K	-7.61 [-18.72, 3.50]	0.228	-0.72 [-1.54, 0.11]	-0.70 [-1.49, 0.11]
NTG-HTG	-3.56 [-15.00, 7.89]	0.729	-0.33 [-1.16, 0.50]	-0.32 [-1.11, 0.49]